

IRON-CONTAINING SEMI-FRITTED ANTIBACTERIAL GLAZES FOR CERAMIC TILES

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The aim of the research is to develop formulations and technological regimes for production of semi-fritted iron-containing glazes for ceramic tiles with antibacterial properties. The topicality of the research and its prospectiveness consists in import substitution of antibacterial additives supplied by American companies, increase of the competitiveness and export potential of the products, widening the scope of application of the product, contribution into scientific research of antibacterial agents, environmental safety and public health.

The composition of raw materials mixture for producing the glaze included the following variable components: aluminoborosilicate frit, antibacterial additives – iron oxide and dolomite. The limit of their content was 20.0–32.5; 5.0–15.0 and 17.5–22.5 wt.%, respectively. The permanent components of composition were feldspar, alumina, kaolin, refractory clay, silica sand. Their total content was 45 wt. %.

The glaze slurry was prepared by joint wet grinding of the components in the laboratory mill Speedy-1 (Italy) to the residue on sieve № 0056 in the amount of 0.4–0.6 wt.% raw material at 35–38 % suspension humidity and glaze density of 1820–1840 kg/m³.

In order to achieve the required rheological properties, sodium tripolyphosphate was added in amount of 0.2 wt.% over 100% of glaze components. A layer of glaze suspension was applied to semi-finished ceramic tiles with its subsequent drying at a temperature of 105±5 °C.

Then the samples were fired in a fast mode in an industrial furnace at a temperature of 1200±5 °C for 60±2 minutes at «Keramin» OJSC.

Visual estimation of the quality of the coatings has shown that the texture and colour of the synthesized coatings depend mainly on amount of the introduced antibacterial additive Fe₂O₃. Thus, the increase of iron oxide content by 15.0 wt. % resulted in the glaze colour change from olive brown to chocolate brown. The shine value is 3–7 %.

One of the most important characteristics of glazes is temperature coefficient of linear expansion that is determined by the strength and length of bonds between the elements of their structure. The ceramic base of the ceramic tiles used in the research was characterised by the thermal expansion coefficient of 82.2·10⁻⁷ K⁻¹. For the investigated compounds iron oxide causes an increase in thermal expansion coefficient values reaching (82.7–88.0)·10⁻⁷ K⁻¹. Thermal expansion of the samples decreased with the increase of Fe₂O₃ content.

The microhardness values of the iron-containing glaze coatings varied between 5312 and 6221 MPa, and increasing with the increase of Fe₂O₃ content in their composition.

The glaze had GA class of chemical resistance. A study of thermal resistance of coatings according to GOST 13996 has shown that they comply with requirements of the standard.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) has established the temperature effects that determine the processes of coatings formation (Fig.1).

The processes common to all the studied glazes were dissociation of the clay minerals, transition of low-temperature quartz to its high-temperature modification (573.2 °C) as well as decomposition of dolomite (735.7 °C) and formation of the crystalline phase of anorthite (828.7 °C) followed by melting of the glaze components (1149.5 °C). For Fe₂O₃ processes are observed due to modification transitions (262.3 °C).

The X-ray phase analysis of the surface layer of the iron-containing glazes has shown that crystalline phase of maghemite γ -Fe₂O₃ predominates in the coatings; they also contain hematite α -Fe₂O₃ and anorthite Ca[Al₂Si₂O₈].

The electron microscopy (EM) examination has also shown that the glaze coatings chip surfaces are represented by crystalline phase and a small number of vitreous phases. Iron-containing glazing coating containing 5–10 wt.% Fe₂O₃ are characterized by a high degree of crystallization. (Fig. 2). The vitreous phase in the image occupies no more than 5 % of its image.

Predominant are tabular crystals differently oriented on the coating surface. The crystals are up to 10 to 50 μm in the largest dimension. The second type of crystals are isometric, sparsely scattered on the glaze surface and are located mainly on the sections between tabular formations that are filled with glass phase. Their dimensions do not exceed 0.2 μm.

Figure 2 – EM images of glaze coatings

The antibacterial activity of developed glazing coatings was researched at the Republican Unitary Enterprise «Scientific and Practical Center of Hygiene» accredited in the National System of Accreditation of the Republic of Belarus. Iron-containing glazes have been found to have the antibacterial activity of 1.42 to the test strain of *Staphylococcus aureus* and 1.09 to that of *Escherichia coli*. The performed studies have shown the prospect of introducing iron oxides instead of silver compounds for producing antibacterial glazes for ceramic tiles.

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